

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON HOSPITAL EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze and empirically prove the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance through the mediating role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) at Bhayangkara Hospital. This research was motivated by the phenomenon of fluctuating employee performance and research gaps regarding the effectiveness of transformational leadership in various organizational contexts. This study employed a quantitative approach with a survey method. The population consisted of 300 hospital employees, with a sample of 171 respondents determined using the Slovin formula. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Squares (PLS) with SmartPLS software. The results showed that transformational leadership did not have a significant effect on either employee performance or the formation of OCB. Conversely, OCB was proven to have a very significant and dominant positive effect on employee performance. Due to the insignificant influence of leadership on OCB, the OCB variable was not proven to act as a mediator in the relationship between transformational leadership and performance. These findings concluded that current high employee performance was driven more by voluntary initiatives and internal employee dedication rather than by the intervention of the supervisor's leadership style.

Keywords: *Employee Performance, Hospital, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Transformational Leadership*

INTRODUCTION

Bhayangkara Hospital has a significant responsibility to provide optimal healthcare to the public and police officers. The quality of these services is highly dependent on its human resources, particularly the performance of medical and non-medical staff. Field observations indicate fluctuations in employee performance, which can hinder the achievement of hospital operational targets. Hospital management needs to understand the determinants that can maintain stability and improve performance. Leadership styles implemented by superiors and voluntary employee behavior outside of formal job descriptions, or Organizational Citizenship Behavior, are often considered key variables in the dynamics of modern organizations. Transformational leadership is believed to bring positive changes to subordinate performance. Various studies support this view with strong empirical evidence. Wang et al. (2011) found a positive relationship between transformational leadership variables and follower performance at both the individual and team levels of analysis. Lowe et al. (1996) demonstrated that transformational leadership scale variables significantly predict work unit effectiveness. Credé et al. (2019) demonstrated a relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance in a large sample of data. Further support comes from Agag et al. (2025) who explained the positive effect of transformational leadership variables on citizenship behavior and task performance. Shang (2023) noted significant direct and indirect effects of transformational leadership variables on employee performance. Norizan et al. (2024) established a link between transformational leadership and organizational performance. Abbas & Ali (2021) found a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and project success. Jyoti & Bhau (2015) supported the positive impact of transformational leadership on work performance. Teoh et al. (2022) found a positive effect of transformational leadership on employee performance in the hospitality industry. Wahid et al. (2017) demonstrated a direct and significant relationship between transformational leadership style and performance.

Other empirical evidence suggests different results and creates a research gap. Udin (2023) reported that transformational leadership variables have no direct effect on adaptive performance and employee performance. Mulki et al. (2005) showed a very low or insignificant correlation between transformational leadership and job performance. Adawiyah & Sopiah (2023) found varying data indicating an insignificant effect on transformational leadership variables. Meiryani et al. (2022) stated that transformational leadership variables have no significant effect on employee performance. Piedade (2021) found that transformational leadership variables have no significant effect on employee performance. The differences in these study results raise the suspicion that another variable acts as an intermediary, namely Organizational Citizenship Behavior. This variable is considered capable of explaining the mechanism by which leadership influences performance, although several studies, such as Bramantya & Muafi (2022), revealed no significant effect between Organizational Citizenship Behavior variables and job performance. The inconsistency of the relationship between these variables underlies the urgency of conducting research on Bhayangkara Hospital employees.

The first hypothesis focuses on the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. Many researchers agree on the positive impact of this leadership style. Wang et al. (2011) found a positive relationship between transformational leadership variables and follower performance. Lowe et al. (1996) demonstrated that transformational leadership scale variables significantly predict work unit effectiveness. Credé et al. (2019) demonstrated a relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. Agag et al. (2025) explained the positive effect of transformational leadership variables on task performance. Shang (2023) noted a significant effect of transformational leadership variables on employee performance. Norizan et al. (2024) established a link between transformational leadership and organizational performance. Abbas & Ali (2021) found a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and project success. Jyoti & Bhau (2015) supported the positive relationship between transformational leadership and work performance. Teoh et al. (2022) found a positive effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. Wahid et al. (2017) demonstrated a direct and significant relationship between transformational leadership style and performance. This hypothesis was proposed to re-examine its significance at Bhayangkara Hospital, given contradictory studies by Udin (2023), Mulki et al. (2005), Adawiyah & Sopiah (2023), Meiryani et al. (2022), and Piedade (2021), which found an insignificant effect. H1: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

The development of the second hypothesis highlights the influence of transformational leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Transformational leaders are considered capable of fostering extra-role behavior in subordinates. Agag et al. (2025) found that transformational leadership variables have a positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Credé et al. (2019) showed a relationship between transformational leadership variables and citizenship behavior. Lee et al. (2023) tested that transformational leadership variables are positively related to organizational citizenship behavior. Nohe & Hertel (2017) confirmed a positive relationship between transformational leadership variables and organizational citizenship behavior. Yuwono et al. (2023) found that transformational leadership variables can directly influence organizational citizenship behavior. Sarwar et al. (2015) proved that transformational leadership variables and organizational citizenship behavior are positively related to each other. Putra (2020) stated that transformational leadership variables can increase organizational citizenship behavior.

Pramudianti & Wijono (2020) explained a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership variables and organizational citizenship behavior. Haghghi & Maleki (2016) showed a significant relationship between transformational leadership style components and organizational citizenship behavior. Aristana et al. (2024) found that transformational leadership variables positively contribute to organizational citizenship behavior. Testing this hypothesis is important because there are different findings from Felani & Nugroho (2023), Nugraha (2021), Mostafa et al. (2018), Soelton (2023), and Ekowati et al. (2013) which stated the effect was insignificant. H2: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The third hypothesis is related to the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on employee performance. Employee volunteerism is believed to contribute to work effectiveness. Haass et al. (2023) stated that organizational citizenship behavior has a significant positive influence on organizational performance. Taufiqurrahman et al. (2021) found that organizational citizenship behavior plays a positive and significant role in employee performance. Dwomoh et al. (2019) explained that organizational citizenship behavior has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Simakhajornboon (2024) found a positive impact of civic virtue and courtesy on performance. Felix & EBOKA (2024) proved a significant impact of organizational citizenship behavior on employee performance. Wei (2014) found a positive relationship between OCBI and OCBO variables and job performance. Mallick et al. (2014) showed that organizational citizenship behavior is positively related to

performance indicators. Organ (2017) indicated a positive contribution of organizational citizenship behavior to performance aspects. Morin & Talbot (2024) found a strong relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and performance quality. This hypothesis needs to be proven on the research object because Bramantya & Muafi (2022) and Abun et al. (2024) reported no significant correlation between the two variables. H3: Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a significant effect on employee performance. The fourth hypothesis tested the mediating role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior. This variable is thought to be a bridge between leadership style and performance. Aristana et al. (2024) demonstrated that organizational citizenship behavior significantly mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. Rahardjo et al. (2021) identified organizational citizenship behavior as a significant mediating variable. Setiawan & Surya (2021) stated that organizational citizenship behavior mediates the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. Prahesti et al. (2017) found that organizational citizenship behavior partially mediates this relationship. Muterera et al. (2024) explained that organizational citizenship behavior functions as a significant mediator. Qalati et al. (2022) tested the mediating effect of organizational citizenship behavior, which strengthens the relationship in the model. Harnani (2017) reported a significant indirect effect coefficient through organizational citizenship behavior. Arifin & Narmaditya (2024) demonstrated that organizational citizenship behavior mediates a positive effect on performance. Tai et al. (2012) explored the mediating role of organizational citizenship behavior variables in the performance relationship. Ng (2016) found general support for this mediation mechanism. This mediation hypothesis was proposed to clarify the contradictory findings of Ekowati et al. (2013), Abrell et al. (2011), Istiqomah & Riani (2021), Khan et al. (2020), and Lai et al. (2020), which found an insignificant or indirect mediation role. H4: Organizational Citizenship Behavior mediates the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance.

The main problem in this study is rooted in the inconsistency of previous studies' results regarding the relationship between leadership, citizenship behavior, and performance. The focus of the problem lies in how transformational leadership affects employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital and whether Organizational Citizenship Behavior plays a role in this mechanism. The researcher formulated a question regarding the significance of the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance directly. The next question discussed the significance of the influence of transformational leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The researcher also questioned the significance of the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on employee performance. The final problem formulation focuses on the role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior in mediating the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital. This research was conducted with the primary objective of analyzing and empirically proving the relationship between the identified variables. The researcher aimed to determine and analyze the significance of the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital. The next objective was to determine and analyze the significance of the influence of transformational leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The researcher also aimed to determine and analyze the significance of the influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on employee performance. The final objective of this research was to determine and analyze the role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior in mediating the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital.

METHOD

This research is a quantitative study with an associative approach. Quantitative methods are used to examine specific populations or samples with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. The associative approach was chosen because this study aims to determine the relationship between variables, namely the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance with *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) as a mediating variable. This research was conducted at Bhayangkara Hospital. The research period included the process of submitting the title, compiling the proposal, distributing the questionnaire, and processing the data and reporting the research results. The population in this study was all 300 employees of Bhayangkara Hospital. This population is considered homogeneous in the context of the study because all members are in one organization, have the same leadership system, and are bound by relatively uniform regulations and work culture. The determination of the sample size in this study used the Slovin formula. This formula is commonly used in social research to determine the sample size from a limited population with a certain level of error. The margin of error used in this study was 5% (0.05), which is considered adequate for management and organizational behavior research. Based on these calculations, the sample size in this study was determined at 171 respondents. The sampling technique used was simple random sampling because the population was considered homogeneous. To

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facilitate data measurement and analysis, the research variables were operationally defined based on indicators adopted from previous studies. The measurement scale used was the Likert Scale 1-5 (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree). Independent Variable: Transformational Leadership (X). Transformational leadership is a leadership style in which the leader inspires and motivates subordinates to achieve extraordinary results. Indicators of this variable include:

1. Idealized Influence: Leaders develop moral standards, generate loyalty, act as role models, are recognized for perseverance, and sacrifice personal interests for the sake of the group (Freire & Azevedo, 2023; Naidoo & Mafora, 2023).
2. Inspirational Motivation: Leaders have a strong vision of the future, build enthusiasm, convey a clear vision, and make subordinates' work meaningful (Freire & Azevedo, 2023; Khirfan & Aziz, 2022; Saeed et al., 2022).
3. Intellectual Stimulation: Leaders encourage followers to be creative, innovative, and experiment to find better approaches (Saeed et al., 2022; Suwarno, 2023).
4. Individual Consideration: Leaders provide personal attention, coach followers, and support staff learning and development opportunities (Huang et al., 2025; Saeed et al., 2022; Suwarno, 2023).

Mediating Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z). OCB is voluntary employee behavior that is not included in formal job descriptions but increases organizational effectiveness. Indicators for this variable include:

1. Altruism: Helping coworkers who are under heavy load, helping with orientation of new people, and being willing to help with work-related problems (Somu & Ali, 2025; Wang, 2011).
2. Conscientiousness : Performing work beyond minimum standards, on time, and adhering to work rules with full dedication (Aliyu & Gebremeskel, 2024; Apostol & Torcino, 2023; Kaul & Singh, 2023) .
3. Sportsmanship: Tolerating discomfort without complaining and maintaining a positive attitude even when things don't go your way (Gupta, 2022; Morin & Talbot, 2024).
4. Courtesy : *Preventing* problems with coworkers, respecting the rights of others, and providing information regarding job changes (Fuller, 2024; Somu & Ali, 2025).
5. Civic *Virtue* : Actively participating in organizational affairs, providing suggestions for improvement, and attending optional meetings (Gupta, 2022; Kaul & Singh, 2023).

Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y). Employee performance is the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties. Indicators for this variable include:

1. Quality: Perfection of work results and quality of service provided (Hadian et al., 2024; Miran & Sumampouw, 2023).
2. Quantity: The amount of work or services completed according to target (Hassan et al., 2022; Miran & Sumampouw, 2023).
3. Punctuality: The ability to complete tasks according to time standards and procedural speed (Hadian et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2022).
4. Effectiveness: The level of efficiency in achieving specified goals (Hadian et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2022).
5. Teamwork: Collaboration and coordination between members (Yusrawati et al., 2023).
6. Commitment: Dedication and attachment to the organization (Yusrawati et al., 2023).
7. Task Performance: The execution of formal job activities such as technical tasks and specific roles (Krijgsheld et al., 2022).
8. Contextual Performance: Interpersonal and voluntary behaviors that support the work environment (Krijgsheld et al., 2022).
9. Adaptive Performance: The ability to adapt to changes in systems or work roles (Krijgsheld et al., 2022).

The data collection method used in this study was a survey using a questionnaire. The questionnaire contained a list of structured statements related to the research variable indicators. The questionnaires were distributed to selected respondents (a sample) both in person (printed) and through digital forms. Respondents were asked to provide responses based on their perceptions of the conditions experienced at Bhayangkara Hospital. The primary analytical tool used to solve the problem formulation and test the hypotheses in this study is *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) with the *Partial Least Squares* (PLS) approach, using SmartPLS software. The rationale for using SEM-PLS is its ability to analyze complex relationship paths between latent variables and its robustness to relatively small to medium sample sizes and data that are not necessarily multivariately normally distributed.

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The stages of data analysis in SEM-PLS include:

1. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (*Outer Model*): This stage aims to test the validity and reliability of the instrument.
 - a. Validity Test: Conducted by examining *the Loading Factor* (convergent validity) and *Average Variance Extracted (AVE)* values. An indicator is considered valid if the loading factor is >0.70 and the AVE is >0.50 . Furthermore, discriminant validity is tested using the Fornell-Larcker or HTMT criteria.
 - b. Reliability Test: Conducted by looking at *the Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability values* . A construct is said to be reliable if the value is > 0.70 .
2. Structural Model Evaluation (*Inner Model*): This stage aims to predict the causal relationship between latent variables. The evaluation is carried out by looking at the *R-Square* (R^2) value to determine how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent, as well as the f^2 (effect size) and Q^2 (predictive relevance) values.
3. Hypothesis Testing: Hypothesis testing is conducted by examining the path coefficient *and* significance values (T-statistic and P-value) through a *bootstrapping procedure* . The hypothesis is accepted if the T-statistic is > 1.96 and the P-value is < 0.05 .

Mediation Test: An indirect effect analysis *was* conducted to determine the role of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior variables* in mediating the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. This test examines the significance of *specific indirect effects* on SmartPLS output results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data analysis in this study was conducted using a variance-based *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) approach or *Partial Least Squares* (PLS) with the assistance of SmartPLS software. Before proceeding to an in-depth evaluation of validity and reliability (*outer model*) and hypothesis testing (*inner model*), the following is a visualization of the path model estimation results (*path diagram*) formed from the research data. This image represents the structural relationships between variables and their constituent indicators after going through the stage of eliminating invalid indicators.

Model Output Image Before Elimination

Model Output Image After Elimination

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Bootstrapping Model Output Image

The figure above shows the construction of a research model consisting of exogenous variables, namely Transformational Leadership (X), and endogenous variables, namely *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (Z) as a mediator and Employee Performance (Y) as the main dependent variable. Visually, the figure provides several fundamental information as follows:

1. The Variable Indicators in the yellow boxes indicate the manifest indicators that are valid and retained in the model to measure each latent variable.
2. Path Coefficients *The* values shown on the arrow lines between latent variables indicate the magnitude of the path coefficient which represents the strength and direction of the direct influence between variables.
3. *R-Square* Value (R^2) The number in the circle of the endogenous variables (OCB and Employee Performance) shows the value of the coefficient of determination, which describes how much of the variance of the variable can be explained by the variables that influence it.

The visualization of this model forms the basic foundation for further statistical testing which will be described in detail in the following sub-chapters on evaluation of measurement models and structural models.

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model, or outer model, is conducted to ensure that the research instrument used is of adequate quality. This process aims to assess the instrument's validity and reliability through three main criteria: convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability. An instrument is considered to meet the requirements if the indicators used are able to measure the variables accurately and consistently.

Summary Table of Measurement Model Evaluation Results

Variables	Key Indicators	AVE (> 0.50)	Cronbach's Alpha (> 0.70)	Composite Reliability (> 0.70)	Status
Transformational Leadership (X)	X ₁ , X ₁₀ , X ₁₂ , X ₁₃ , X ₁₅	0.557	0.954	0.957	Valid & Reliable
Org. Citizenship Behavior (Z)	All Indicators	0.765	0.846	0.906	Valid & Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	All Indicators	0.632	0.961	0.965	Valid & Reliable

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Discriminant Validity Summary Table (HTMT)

Relationship between variables	HTMT Value	Terms and Conditions	Status
Z (<i>OCB</i>) against Y (<i>Performance</i>)	0.863	< 0.90	Fulfilled
X (<i>Leadership</i>) to Y (<i>Performance</i>)	0.105	< 0.90	Fulfilled
X (<i>Leadership</i>) towards Z (<i>OCB</i>)	0.100	< 0.90	Fulfilled

1. Convergent Validity.

This validity is assessed from the Outer Loadings and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The data shows that all indicators retained in the model, including indicators X1 , X10 , X12 , X13 , and X15 in the Transformational Leadership variable, have loading factor values above 0.70 or close to that value. Specifically for indicator X15 with a value of 0.670, this figure is still declared valid and acceptable in the context of exploratory research. In addition, the AVE values for all variables Employee Performance (0.632), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (0.765), and Transformational Leadership (0.557) are above the threshold of 0.50, which indicates that convergent validity is well met.

2. Construct Reliability.

Instrument consistency was measured using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability with the requirement that the value must be greater than 0.70. The test results showed that the Employee Performance variable had a very high level of reliability (Cronbach's Alpha 0.961; Composite Reliability 0.965). Likewise, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable (Cronbach's Alpha 0.846; Composite Reliability 0.906) and Transformational Leadership (Cronbach's Alpha 0.954; Composite Reliability 0.957). All variables were declared highly reliable.

3. Discriminant Validity.

Discriminant validity was tested using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) method with the requirement that the value must be below 0.90. The analysis results show that the HTMT ratio between variables Z and Y is 0.863, X and Y is 0.105, and X and Z is 0.100. Since all values are below 0.90, it is concluded that each variable is distinctively different from each other and discriminant validity is met.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

After the measurement model evaluation is complete, the next stage is the evaluation of the structural model, or inner model. This evaluation aims to predict causal relationships between latent variables and assess the quality of the constructed structural model. There are three main criteria in this evaluation: Collinearity Statistics (VIF) to ensure there is no multicollinearity bias, the Coefficient of Determination (R²) to measure the model's predictive power, and Effect Size (f²) to assess the magnitude of substantive influence between variables.

Summary Table of Structural Model Evaluation Results

Evaluation Criteria	Variables / Relationship Paths	Mark	Category / Interpretation
Collinearity (VIF) (Requirement < 5.0)	Z (<i>OCB</i>) → Y (<i>Performance</i>)	1,011	Multicollinearity Free
	X (<i>Leadership</i>) → Y (<i>Performance</i>)	1,011	Multicollinearity Free
	X (<i>Leadership</i>) → Z (<i>OCB</i>)	1,000	Multicollinearity Free
R-Square (R ²)	Employee Performance (Y)	0.647	Moderate to Strong
	Org. Citizenship Behavior (Z)	0.010	Very weak
Effect Size (f ²)	Z (<i>OCB</i>) → Y (<i>Performance</i>)	1,804	Big Effect
	X (<i>Leadership</i>) → Y (<i>Performance</i>)	0.002	Very Small Effect / There isn't any
	X (<i>Leadership</i>) → Z (<i>OCB</i>)	0.011	Very Small Effect / There isn't any

1. Collinearity Statistics (VIF) The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value is used to detect the presence of multicollinearity between independent variables in the model. The results of the analysis show that all VIF values are very low and close to 1, namely 1.011 for the Z to Y and X to Y paths, and 1.000 for the X to Z path. This value is far below the threshold of 5.0 (or the strict criterion of <3.0), which indicates that this model is completely free from the problem of collinearity bias.

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2. Coefficient of Determination (R²) The R² value indicates the ability of the independent variable to explain the variability of the dependent variable. For the Employee Performance variable (Y), the R² value is 0.647. This means that 64.7% of the variation in employee performance can be explained jointly by Transformational Leadership and *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB). This figure is included in the moderate to strong category, indicating that the model has good predictive power on performance. For the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable (Z), the R² value is 0.010. This means that only 1.0% of the variation in OCB can be explained by Transformational Leadership. This value is classified as very weak, indicating that in the context of this sample, Transformational Leadership has almost no impact on the formation of employee OCB behavior.
3. Effect Size (f²) The f² value evaluates the magnitude of the substantive influence of the predictor variables on the dependent variable. The Z (OCB) → Y (Performance) path has an f² value of 1.804, which is categorized as a large effect. This indicates that OCB has a very strong and dominant impact on employee performance. The X (Leadership) → Y (Performance) path has an f² value of 0.002, and the X (Leadership) → Z (OCB) path has a value of 0.011. Both of these values are categorized as very small effects or considered non-existent, which confirms the weak role of transformational leadership in this structural model.

Hypothesis Testing

The final stage in evaluating a structural model is hypothesis testing to determine the significance of the influence between variables. This testing is performed by analyzing the *Path Coefficient value* to determine the direction of the relationship, as well as the *T-Statistics* and *P-Values* resulting from the *bootstrapping procedure* to determine significance. The hypothesis is declared accepted or significant if the *T-Statistics value* is greater than 1.96 and the *P-Values value* is less than 0.05 at a 5% error level. The following table summarizes the results of the direct and indirect effects tests .

Summary Table of Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Relationship Path	Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Value	Information
H ₁	Leadership Transfer (X) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.025	0.288	0.774	Rejected (Not Significant)
H ₂	Transf. Leadership (X) → OCB (Z)	0.102	0.711	0.477	Rejected (Not Significant)
H ₃	OCB (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.802	24,388	0.000	Accepted (Significant)
H ₄	Transf. Leadership (X) → OCB (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.082	0.716	0.474	Rejected (Not Significant)

Based on the table above, the interpretation of the hypothesis testing results is as follows:

1. The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance (H1) . The test results show a positive but insignificant influence with a P-Value of 0.774 (> 0.05). This indicates that the transformational leadership style implemented at Bhayangkara Hospital does not directly improve employee performance. This finding is in line with the research results of Udin (2023) and Meiryani et al. (2022).
2. The Effect of Transformational Leadership on OCB (H2) . The analysis results show a positive but insignificant effect with a P-Value of 0.477 (>0.05). This means that transformational leaders in the context of this study have not been successful in significantly encouraging the development of extra-role behavior or Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in employees. These results support the findings of the study by Felani & Nugroho (2023).
3. The Influence of OCB on Employee Performance (H3) . The test results prove a highly significant positive influence with a high T-Statistics value (24.388) and a P-Value of 0.000 (<0.05). The path coefficient of 0.802 indicates a strong influence, proving that OCB behavior is a major determinant of high employee performance. This finding is consistent with research by Haass et al. (2023) and Taufiqurrahman et al. (2021).
4. The Mediating Role of OCB (H4) . The results of the specific indirect effects test showed an insignificant value with a P-Value of 0.474 (> 0.05). Thus, the OCB variable was not proven to mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. This mediation failure occurred because

the initial path from leadership to OCB (H2) was insignificant, so a mediation mechanism could not be formed. This conclusion is in line with the findings of Ekowati et al. (2013).

Based on the research results, it can be seen that employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital is significantly driven by employee volunteerism (OCB). However, the transformational leadership style currently implemented has not had a significant impact, either on directly improving performance or on fostering OCB behavior.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance. The results of the first hypothesis test indicate that transformational leadership does not significantly influence employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital. Operationally, this finding indicates that the implementation of leadership indicators such as *idealized influence* and *intellectual stimulation* applied by hospital leaders has not been able to directly impact the quantity or quality of employee work output. Although leaders may have attempted to be *role models* or encourage innovation, this does not appear to immediately improve time efficiency or the effectiveness of completing medical and administrative tasks in the field. This condition may be caused by the characteristics of the hospital work environment which is highly standardized with strict *Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)*, so that the room for innovation resulting from transformational leadership is limited and does not have a direct impact on routine performance metrics. This empirical finding is inconsistent with the view of Wang et al. (2011) who found a positive relationship between transformational leadership and follower performance, nor the findings of Wahid et al. (2017) who proved a direct and significant relationship between transformational leadership style and performance. Other studies such as Credé et al. (2019), Agag et al. (2025), Shang (2023), Norizan et al. (2024), Abbas & Ali (2021), Jyoti & Bhau (2015), and Teoh et al. (2022) also consistently support the positive influence of leadership on performance, which is different from the conditions at Bhayangkara Hospital. Conversely, the results of this study actually support the argument of Udin (2023) who stated that transformational leadership variables do not have a direct or significant influence on employee performance. This also strengthens the findings of Mulki et al. (2005) which showed a very low or insignificant correlation, and is in line with the conclusions of Adawiyah & Sopiah (2023), Meiryani et al. (2022), and Piedade (2021) who found that in certain contexts, this leadership style is not a major predictor of employee performance.

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)*. The second hypothesis stating that transformational leadership has a significant effect on OCB of Bhayangkara Hospital employees was rejected. The data showed that a leadership style oriented towards *inspirational motivation* and *individualized consideration* did not successfully stimulate extra-role employee behaviors, such as *altruism* or *civic virtue*. Practically, this means that even though leaders provide personal attention or an inspiring vision, this does not necessarily make employees willing to perform tasks outside their job descriptions, such as helping overworked colleagues or volunteering to participate in hospital activities outside of work hours. Rigid hierarchical factors or the already very high functional workload in the medical environment may hinder the transfer of transformational values into volunteer behavior. These results contradict the majority of the literature, such as the findings of Agag et al. (2025) who found a positive influence of leadership on OCB across cultures, as well as studies by Nohe & Hertel (2017), Yuwono et al. (2023), and Aristana et al. (2024) confirmed that transformational leadership positively contributes to OCB.

Other studies by Credé et al. (2019), Lee et al. (2023), Sarwar et al. (2015), Putra (2020), Pramudianti & Wijono (2020), and Haghighi & Maleki (2016) also showed a significant relationship. However, the findings at Bhayangkara Hospital align with the research of Felani & Nugroho (2023) which stated there was no significant influence between transformational leadership variables on OCB. These results are also supported by Nugraha (2021) who found an insignificant effect, as well as the findings of Soelton (2023) who proved that transformational leadership had no significant impact on citizenship behavior. This is also consistent with Mostafa et al. (2018) and Ekowati et al. (2013) who showed a direct relationship between this leadership style and employee volunteer initiatives. The Influence of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)* on Employee Performance. The results of the study prove that *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)* has a positive and highly significant influence on the performance of Bhayangkara Hospital employees. This is the most dominant finding in the research model. Operationally, high levels of *conscientiousness* (awareness) where employees work beyond minimum standards, as well as high levels of *sportsmanship* (sportsmanship) by not complaining about inconveniences, significantly improve performance indicators such as the timeliness of service and the quality of nursing/medical care. When employees help each other (*altruism*) and prevent interpersonal problems (*courtesy*)

), the hospital workflow becomes smoother, operational obstacles are reduced, and ultimately individual and unit performance targets are achieved more effectively. These findings confirm the argument of Haass et al. (2023) who stated that OCB variables have a significant positive influence on organizational performance. This is also in line with Taufiqurrahman et al. (2021) and Dwomoh et al. (2019) who explain the crucial role of OCB on employee performance. This empirical evidence is also supported by Felix & EBOKA (2024), Wei (2014), and Mallick et al. (2014) who showed a positive relationship between OCB dimensions and performance indicators. Furthermore, this finding strengthens the indications from Organ (2017) and Morin & Talbot (2024) regarding the strong contribution of citizenship behavior to performance quality. These results reject the assumptions of the studies by Bramantya & Muafi (2022), Abun et al. (2024), and some of the findings of Dwomoh et al. (2019) who stated there was no significant correlation between OCB and work performance, proving that in the context of Bhayangkara Hospital, extra-role behavior is a vital asset for productivity.

The Mediating Role of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB). Based on the mediation path analysis, it was found that *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* was not proven to mediate the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance. This failure of the mediation function occurred because the main requirement for mediation was not met, namely the inability of transformational leadership to significantly influence OCB in the initial stage ($H2$ was rejected). This means that the high performance of Bhayangkara Hospital employees driven by OCB was not the result of the intervention of the superior's transformational leadership style, but rather emerged from other factors not examined in this model (e.g., intrinsic motivation, medical professional ethics, or a culture of unity). Leaders were unable to successfully use OCB as a mechanism to boost performance. This conclusion differs from the research of Aristana et al. (2024), Rahardjo et al. (2021), and Setiawan & Surya (2021) which successfully proved the significant role of OCB as a mediating variable. Similarly, the findings of Prahesti et al. (2017), Muterera et al. (2024), Qalati et al. (2022), Harnani (2017), Arifin & Narmaditya (2024), Tai et al. (2012), and Ng (2016) supported this mediation mechanism. However, the results of this study support the conclusion of Ekowati et al. (2013) who explicitly stated that OCB variables do not mediate the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. This phenomenon is also in line with the explanation of Abrell et al. (2011) regarding the time constraints of behavioral change that cause the mediation effect to be insignificant, as well as the findings of Istiqomah & Riani (2021) who found a break in the influence path from leadership to OCB. This is also in line with the implications of the studies of Khan et al. (2020) and Lai et al. (2020) who identified the insignificance of the mediation role in similar relationship models.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing, this study concludes that employee performance at Bhayangkara Hospital is predominantly determined by employee voluntary initiatives or *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB), not by the applied transformational leadership style. Empirical findings indicate that OCB has a very significant and strong positive impact as the main predictor of performance improvement, meaning that the higher the behavior of mutual assistance, accuracy, and sportsmanship of employees, the higher the quality and quantity of hospital services. Conversely, transformational leadership was proven to have no significant influence, either directly on employee performance or in fostering OCB behavior, so the hypothesis regarding the role of OCB as a mediating variable was also not proven. This indicates that work effectiveness in the Bhayangkara Hospital environment is currently driven more by the internal awareness and professional dedication of the employees themselves, regardless of the efforts of inspirational motivation or intellectual stimulation carried out by the leadership.

Suggestion

Suggestions that can be put forward based on the limitations and managerial implications of this study are focused on efforts to maintain performance stability and the development of research models in the future. Considering the vital role of OCB which is proven to be very significant but not influenced by transformational leadership, the management of Bhayangkara Hospital is advised to design alternative strategies to maintain this behavior, for example through strengthening a collaborative work culture, a *reward system* that appreciates teamwork, or *soft-skill training*, and needs to re-evaluate the effectiveness of the current leadership communication pattern. For further research, it is recommended to no longer only focus on transformational leadership style as the only predictor, but also explore other antecedent variables that have the potential to influence OCB considering the very low *R-Square value* of this variable in this study such as intrinsic motivation,

job satisfaction, organizational climate, or medical professional ethics, as well as expanding the scope of the sample to several different hospitals to obtain a more comprehensive generalization of the results.

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